

RECIPROCITY OR THE ART OF CONNECTING

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How can veterinary students learn to approach stakeholders, patient owners, lay public and other non-vets in ways that acknowledge the expertise of all involved? What can a vet learn from the owner, the farmer, the hoofsmith, the animal welfare organization activist? And how can this be approached in a way that doesn't discount the science-based knowledge a vet brings to the table? These hard questions are part of veterinary professionalization.

Community engaged learning (CEL) can provide useful insights in this area. A key concept in CEL is reciprocity, in which everyone involved in the process brings knowledge and experiences to the table and learns from one another: students, societal partners and teachers. This can lead to benefits for all parties involved by increasing influence in project outcomes, and co-creation of new ideas or projects (1,2); discussing with veterinarians about how to approach and improve veterinary care can also

empower owners, farmers and stakeholders in future discussions with veterinary professionals.

Thinking about reciprocity in the setting of a health care professional like a veterinarian can be challenging. After all, the veterinarian brings knowledge to the conversation: how to heal an animal that has been brought to their practice with a fracture. How to plan and execute a sound vaccination strategy for a poultry farm. How to work toward healthy genetics in companion animal breeds. There is also a cross-link with Equality, Diversity and Inclusion that I'll return to in a later post, where women or those with ethnically diverse backgrounds can have difficulty being taken seriously in their knowledge.

When veterinary student is aware of the strengths and limits of their own knowledge, there is a lot to be learned from societal partners; one profound example is looking into where and why veterinary care is lacking. In a poignant example, Tan and colleagues reported going into areas with indigenous populations with veterinary students from a conscious attitude of respect, learning from horse care practices and being open to how the lack of trust in (veterinary) medical care came to be in a group in Canada (3).

There are lessons to be learned about approaching groups that may lack veterinary care through this example with its own charged history. It is not about not simply offering care or teaching about basic animal care, but also listening to why it is not available (or used) in the first place. Try to understand the root of the problem by including the knowledge of all involved; in short, reciprocal learning.

Experience with each of these kinds of reciprocity is beneficial to societal partners by giving opportunities to interact with and influence future veterinary care, and for future veterinarians in developing the social context and skills needed to constructively enter into societal discourse at personal, local or even international levels (4). Sometimes learning is about sitting next to someone and looking forward together.

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